

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.13889448

Influence of Social Media on Provocative Sexual Behaviour among Undergraduate Female Students in Rivers State Universities

¹Onisoya Maclean PhD & ²Awajiokinor Ekrika Mbaba PhD

¹Department of Educational Psychology, Guidance and Counselling
Faculty of Education,
Rivers State University, Port Harcourt, Nigeria
MACLEAN.ONISOYA@ust.edu.ng

²Department of Educational Foundations
Faculty of Education,
Rivers State University, Port Harcourt, Nigeria
Awajiokinor.Mbaba@ust.edu.ng

ABSTRACT

This study examined the influence of social media on provocative sexual behaviour as perceived by undergraduate female students in Rivers State universities. The study adopted descriptive research design. Three (3) research questions and three (3) hypotheses guided the study. The population was 11,061 undergraduate female students from Rivers State universities (Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education). The sample size of 400 female students was obtained through Taro Yamene formula, purposive sampling techniques was adopted to sample the research subjects. Social Media on Provocative Sexual Behaviour Scale” (SMPSBS) was used for data collection. The reliability of the instrument was determined using test-retest method which yielded reliability coefficients of 0.78. Mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions, while the Independent t-test was used to test the hypotheses. The findings of the study revealed that there was no significant difference in the influence of Whatsapp, Facebook and Instagram on provocative sexual behaviour as perceived by undergraduate female students in Rivers State universities based on identity. Therefore, the researchers recommend that universities administration should establish rules and regulation prohibiting provocative sexual behaviour such as wearing short skirts, wearing sleeveless blouse, seductive sitting and exposure of upper region of their body and sharing via social media.

Keywords: Social media, provocative, sexual behaviour, Whatsapp, Facebook, Instagram

INTRODUCTION

Provocative sexual behavior among undergraduates is shaped by environmental and social structures. It is believed that mental and emotional aspects of sexual well-being are important aspects of sexual health. However, the undergraduate student perceived and engaged in provocative sexual behaviour is also influenced by several psychological and social factors such as self-image and self-concept. The sexual self-concept is defined as the cognitive perspective concerning the sexual aspects of “self” (Potki et al., 2017). Most undergraduates engaged in various sexual behaviours that may present serious dangers to their academics, sexual behavior may also increase the likelihood of sexually transmitted infections (STIs). Sexual risky behavior among Nigerian undergraduate students is on the increase (Daramola et al., 2017). A great deal of research attention has been devoted to understanding what puts students at risk for these outcomes, given their enormous social, economic, and public

health consequences. Yet it is clear that we need to know more and more to address risky and provocative sexual activity among undergraduate students.

The truth remains that internet and social media platforms have negative health consequences due to false belief of privacy leading to more provocative behavior and discussions around drinking, sex, violence, suicide ideation and bullying. Landry et al. (2019) in a study found that undergraduate students who sent or received more than 100 SMS per day were significantly more likely to ever have vaginal sex and students who logged in to a social networking account at least once per day were significantly more likely to ever have vaginal sex. Kolan et al. (2018) reported that 75% of texters and 72% of social networkers sending messages or photos that they would not want their parents to see, while 56.4% admitted to using texting or social networking to find a place to gather without parental supervision, for example, to drink alcohol (41.5%) or to meet for sex (27.4%).

McQuail, (2020) described social media as the means of communication that operates on a large scale, reaching and involving virtually everyone in a society to a greater or lesser degree". It is a large scale medium. Media is the plural form of medium which means a channel or instrument through which something (information, message, and signals) is transmitted or carried. Agreeing with the above submission, Pomfowaa and Dotse (2023) asserted that social media is an internet-based form of communication technologies for either small group of people or a significantly larger audience. These technologies, such as blogs, video-sharing platforms (such as YouTube), presentation-sharing platforms (such as SlideShare), social networking platforms (such as Facebook and LinkedIn), instant messaging platforms (such as Skype), and groupware platforms (such as Google Docs). These social media platforms allow users to have conversations, share information and create web content. There are many forms of social media, including blogs, micro-blogs, wikis, social networking sites, photo-sharing sites, instant messaging, video-sharing sites, podcasts, widgets, virtual worlds, and more. Social media is a form of computed-mediated communication, like email and online chat forums that enable content to be exchanged between people via the internet (Pomfowaa & Dotse, 2023).

Sexual behavior refers to the expression of an individual's eroticism and/ or emotional attachment with reference to the sex and gender of the partner involved in sexual activity. Omoni and Onoyase (2019) viewed sexual behavior as the manner in which human beings experience and express their sexuality and this involves a number of activities such as sexual intercourse, non-penetrative sex, oral sex, hugging, kissing and holding of hands amongst others. Different sexual acts and behaviours, other than penetrative penis-vaginal intercourses are used by different people to express their sexual urges. Sexual behavior varies from one culture to another and from one person to another.

Olawade et al. (2024) defined sexual behavior as the ways individuals think, feel and behave or intend to behave with regard to the expression of their sexuality. Sexual behaviours as feelings about sexual arousal, interests in exploring sexual behaviours, and the desire for commitment. It is regarded as an individual's willingness to place limits on the range of human sexual expression. Every individual is entitled to his or her sexual right. Nevertheless, there are acceptable and unacceptable sexual behaviours within a given society. Such deviant sexual behavior are prevalent among university students. These include indecent assault (touching of breasts or buttocks), cuddling, rape, pre-marital sex, watching of pornographic film, displaying of nude pictures, engaging in incest, multi-sex partners, oral sex, web-dating, engaging in sex with older persons (Sugar Daddy/Mummy), indecent dress code, peeping, masturbation, exhibitionism, voyeurism, and use of objects to satisfy sexual urges (Ijadunola et al., 2023).

Obiunu (2014) and Popa and Delcea (2019) listed the following sexual behaviour: sexual abuse (forceful carnal knowledge of a victim), voyeurism (sexual practice of gaining sexual pleasure from watching or peeping others when they are naked or engaged in sexual activities), masturbation (sexual desires by self-help), pornography (watching sexual videos, books or magazines), lesbianism (the act of a female making love to a person of the same sex), homosexuality (same-sex sexual relations), transgender (is a general term that describes people whose gender identity, or their internal sense of being male, female, or something else, does not match the sex they were assigned at birth), and incest (sexual behaviour between family members or close relatives). Types of students provocative behaviour include; wearing short skirts (mini-shirt is a woman's short skirt with the hemline several

inches above the knee),wearing sleeveless blouse, seductive walking, seductive sitting, exposure of breast and punk hairs

Different scholars have researched on the link between social media and academic performance, not much have been done on social media and provocative sexual behaviour among students. Uzobo et al. (2020) conducted a study on social media use and sexual behaviour of undergraduate students in a Nigerian University. The study found that the use of whatsapp (OR = 0.254, $p < 0.05$), instagram (OR=0.254, $p < 0.05$, time spent on the social media (OR=0.123, $p < 0.05$) were significantly associated with high-risk provocative sexual behaviour of students. The study concluded that use of social media especially whatsapp influenced the provocative sexual needs of students.

Adegboyega (2019) examined the influence of social media on sexual behavior of youth in kwara State. The study found that social media has considerable influenced on the sexual behaviour of the youths in Kwara State. The study also found that social media had a significant positive correlation with provocative sexual behaviours of the youth. Social media leads student to the act of sending erotic messages, watching pornographic films and movies and risky sexual behaviour such as masturbation. Finally, the study found that there was a significant difference between social media influence on sexual behaviour of youths (student) based on garden, age and university attended. The use of Whatsapp was rated the most used social media in sending and watching provocative pornographic films. The study discovered that friends send their node pictures via Whatsapp.

Asyraaf and Badayai (2022) investigated the relationship between technology, social media and sexual behavior among university students. This study aims investigated the relationships between technology usage and social media exposure towards provocative sexual behavior among university students in Malaysia. The study revealed that there was a significant, positive relationship between social media exposure and provocative sexual behavior and for technology usage there was no significant relationships towards sexual behavior.

Onasoga et al. (2020) examined the influence of social media use on sexual behavior of undergraduate in Ilorin, Kwara State, Nigeria. The study revealed that 100% of the respondents had access to the internet and 32% of the respondents had high exposure sexual content on social media via Whatsapp, Facebook, twitter, myspace and 2go and a significant difference was observed between males and females with more males using social media for sexual purposes than female, study showed that there is a significant association between exposure to sexual content on social media and risky sexual behaviour amongst female undergraduate students. Owen et al. (2020 carried out an investigation on undergraduates' utilization of social networking media and sexual behaviours in higher education: A case study. The finding of the study revealed that undergraduates in Nigerian universities are largely exposed to a substantial amount of sexual contents on various social media networks; and that this exposure negatively influenced their psychology towards sex as manifested in areas of dating and sexual activities.

Statement of the Problem

The high rate of provocative sexual behaviour among university undergraduates in Nigeria has led to the moral deterioration in the Nigeria universities and the society at large and has also led to unwanted pregnancies, abortions, Sexually Transmitted Diseases (STDs), death resorting from sexual activities, dropping out of school, poor attendance to lectures, poor academic performance or achievement, poor health conditions, permanent deformity, self-guilt, isolation, stigmatization, despair or depression, poor self- concept, negative self-image, teenage motherhood, single parenting, premarital sex among undergraduates.

The undergraduate students are involved in several provocative sexual behaviour such as rape, voyeurism, masturbation, lesbianism, homosexuality, transgender, sodomy, fetishism, oral sex and incest all in the name of achieving sexual satisfaction or obtaining financial gratifications stressing that economy is hard. These sexual inclinations are observed in female undergraduate students dressing to reveal their sexuality such as wearing mini-shirts, wearing bangles, wearing sleeveless blouses, exposure of breast, walking seductively or sitting seductively. Most of these behaviours are learnt from social media platforms and following some superstars. The situation if not given adequate attention may worsen the very purpose why these students are in the universities and can lead to a breakdown of societal norms.

The influence of social media through Whatsapp, Facebook and Instagram cannot be underestimated as sexual video clips are shared among friends has led to most cases of gang rape. The trauma of rape can be devastating that can cause academic underachievement to a victim. It is against this background that the study investigated the influence of social media on provocative sexual behaviour among undergraduate female students in Rivers State Universities.

Objectives of the Study

The aim of the study was to investigate the influence of social media on provocative sexual behaviour as perceived by undergraduate female students in Rivers State universities. In specific terms, it will:

1. Investigate the influence of whatsapp use on provocative sexual behaviour as perceived by undergraduate female students in Rivers State universities based on the identity of the university.
2. Determine the influence of facebook on provocative sexual behaviour as perceived by undergraduate female students in Rivers State universities based on the identity of the university.
3. Establish the influence of instagram on provocative sexual behaviour as perceived by undergraduate female students in Rivers State universities based on the identity of the university.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the extent of the influence of Whatsapp use on provocative sexual behaviour as perceived by undergraduate female students in Rivers State universities based on the identity of the university?
2. What is the extent of the influence of Facebook on provocative sexual behaviour as perceived by undergraduate female students in Rivers State universities based on the identity of the university?
3. What is the extent of the influence of Instagram on provocative sexual behaviour as perceived by undergraduate female students in Rivers State universities based on the identity of the university?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses are to guide the study:

1. There is no significant influence of Whatsapp on provocative sexual behaviour as perceived by undergraduate female students in Rivers State universities based on identity
2. There is no significant influence of Facebook on provocative sexual behaviour as perceived by undergraduate female students in Rivers State universities based on the identity of the university.
3. There is no significant influence of Instagram on provocative sexual behaviour as perceived by undergraduate female students in Rivers State universities based on the identity of the university.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The population of the study consisted of all the female undergraduate in the Ignatius Ajuru University of Education and Rivers State University. The population of female undergraduate students in Ignatius Ajuru University of Education is 4,703 (source: Nigerian University Statistic, 2020), the number of female Undergraduate students in Rivers State University is 6,358 (source: www.rsu.edu.ng, 2022), thus, the total population of female undergraduate students of 11,061 is used for the study.

The study adopted the stratified random sampling blended with purposive sampling to group the female students according to the female hostels in the universities. The Taro Yemeni sample size

calculation was used to determine the sample size of the female undergraduate students, the sample size is 386 but approximated to 400.

The instrument for data collection for this study was a self-structured questionnaire titled “Social Media on Provocative Sexual Behaviour Scale” (SMPSBS). It consisted of three sections; A, B and C. Section A comprises personal information such as name of university and level of study. Section B consists of item statements on the influence of psychosocial variables while section C consists of item statements on the influence of the social media on provocative sexual behavior of undergraduate students in Rivers State universities, Nigeria. The SMPSBS was responded to on a four (4) point rating scale of Very High Extent (VHE) = 4, HE (HE) = 3, Low Extent (LE) = 2, and Very Low Extent (VLE) = 1.

The instrument was tested for reliability through a test-retest method, with a reliability coefficient for $r = 0.78$ ascertained through the Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) statistic. The copies of the questionnaire were administered and retrieved from the respondents at the various schools selected in the sample. The total of 400 copies of the questionnaire administered and 400 copies retrieved were properly filled, and thus used for further analysis.

The collected data was analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions while the independent t-test was used in test the hypotheses analysis of the hypotheses was tested for statistical significance at 0.05 alpha level.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: *What is the extent of the influence of Whatsapp use on provocative sexual behavior as perceived by undergraduate female students in Rivers State universities based on the identity of the university?*

Table 1: Mean Rating and Standard Deviation of the Extent of the Influence of Whatsapp Use on Provocative Sexual Behaviour as Perceived by Undergraduate Female Students in Rivers State Universities Based on the Identity of the University

S/N	Items	IAUE (n=192)			RSU (n=208)		
		\bar{x}	SD	Decision	\bar{x}	SD	Decision
.1	Whatsapp friends usually introduced other female students to the wearing of short skirts and bangles on the ankles.	3.18	0.76	VHE	3.14	0.78	VHE
.2	Whatsapp friends usually introduced other female students to the wearing of sleeveless blouse and exposure of breast.	3.16	0.77	VHE	3.13	0.78	VHE
.3	Whatsapp friends usually introduced other female students to seductive walking and seductive sitting.	3.15	0.77	VHE	3.13	0.80	VHE
.4	Whatsapp friends usually introduced other female students to the wearing of tight trousers and pinking of different hair styles.	3.11	0.78	VHE	3.13	0.81	VHE
Grand Mean		3.15			3.13		

Criterion Mean = 2.5, Mean: 1.0-1.99 = VLE, 2.0-2.49=LE, 2.5-2.99 = HE, 3.00-4.00=VHE.

Table 1 shows the extent of the influence of Whatsapp use on provocative sexual behavior as perceived by undergraduate female students in Rivers State universities based on the identity of the university. The result from female undergraduates from IAUE showed that, the majority of the respondents indicated VHE for items 1-4, with their mean scores greater than or equal to the criterion mean (2.50) and within the range of 3.00–4.00. On the other hand, the result from female undergraduates from RSU showed that, the majority of the respondents indicated VHE for items 1–4, with their mean scores greater than or equal to the criterion mean (2.50) and within the range of 3.00–4.00.

The grand mean of 3.15 for undergraduates from IAUE, and 3.13 for undergraduates from RSU, implied that the extent of the influence of Whatsapp use on provocative sexual behaviours as perceived by undergraduate female students in Rivers State universities based on the identity of the university is to a very high extent.

Research Question 2: *What is the extent of the influence of Facebook on provocative sexual behaviours perceived by undergraduate female students in Rivers State universities based on the identity of the university?*

Table 2: Mean Rating and Standard Deviation of the Extent of the Influence of Facebook on Provocative Sexual Behaviour as Perceived by Undergraduate Female Students in Rivers State Universities Based on the Identity of the University

S/N	Items	IAUE (n=192)			RSU (n=208)		
		\bar{x}	SD	Decision	\bar{x}	SD	Decision
.5	Facebook friends usually introduced other female students to the wearing of short skirts and bangles on the ankles.	3.19	0.81	VHE	3.23	0.76	VHE
.6	Facebook friends usually introduced other female students to the wearing of sleeveless blouse and exposure of breast.	3.11	0.84	VHE	3.13	0.80	VHE
.7	Facebook friends usually introduced other female students to seductive walking and seductive sitting.	3.14	0.84	VHE	3.16	0.82	VHE
.8	Facebook friends usually introduced other female students to the wearing of tight trousers and pinking of different hair styles.	3.01	0.85	VHE	2.98	0.85	HE
Grand Mean		3.11			3.13		

Criterion Mean = 2.5, Mean: 1.0-1.99 = VLE, 2.0-2.49=LE, 2.5-2.99 = HE, 3.00-4.00=VHE.

Table 2 shows the extent of the influence of Facebook on provocative sexual behaviours perceived by undergraduate female students in Rivers State universities based on the identity of the university. The result from female undergraduates from IAUE showed that, the majority of the respondents indicated VHE for items 5-8, with their mean scores greater than or equal to the criterion mean (2.50) and within the range of 3.00–4.00. On the other hand, the result from female undergraduates from RSU showed that, the majority of the respondents indicated VHE for items 5–8, with their mean scores greater than or equal to the criterion mean (2.50) and within the range of 3.00–4.00, and HE for item 36, with their mean scores greater than or equal to the criterion mean (2.50) and within the range of 2.50–2.99.

The grand mean of 3.11 for undergraduates from IAUE, and 3.13 for undergraduates from RSU, implied that the extent of the influence Facebook use on provocative sexual behaviours perceived by undergraduate female students in Rivers State universities based on the identity of the university is to a very high extent.

Research Question 3: *What is the extent of the influence of Instagram on provocative sexual behavior as perceived by undergraduate female students in Rivers State universities based on the identity of the university?*

Table 3: Mean Rating and Standard Deviation of the Extent of the Influence of Instagram on Provocative Sexual Behaviour as Perceived by Undergraduate Female Students in Rivers State Universities Based on the Identity of the University

S/N	Items	IAUE (n=192)			RSU (n=208)		
		\bar{x}	SD	Decision	\bar{x}	SD	Decision
.9	Instagram friends usually introduced other female students to the wearing of short skirts and bangles on the ankles.	3.03	1.04	VHE	3.00	1.03	VHE
.10	Instagram friends usually introduced other female students to the wearing of sleeveless blouse and exposure of breast.	3.17	0.76	VHE	3.19	0.77	VHE
.11	Instagram friends usually introduced other female students to seductive walking and seductive sitting.	3.15	0.76	VHE	3.19	0.76	VHE
.12	Instagram friends usually introduced other female students to the wearing of tight trousers and pinking of different hair styles.	3.15	0.77	VHE	3.21	0.74	VHE
Grand Mean		3.13			3.15		

Criterion Mean = 2.5, Mean: 1.0-1.99 = VLE, 2.0-2.49=LE, 2.5-2.99 = HE, 3.00-4.00=VHE.

Table 3 shows the extent of the influence of Instagram on provocative sexual behaviours perceived by undergraduate female students in Rivers State universities based on the identity of the university. The result from female undergraduates from IAUE showed that, the majority of the respondents indicated VHE for items 9-12, with their mean scores greater than or equal to the criterion mean (2.50) and within the range of 3.00–4.00. On the other hand, the result from female undergraduates from RSU showed that, the majority of the respondents indicated VHE for items 9–12, with their mean scores greater than or equal to the criterion mean (2.50) and within the range of 3.00–4.00. The grand mean of 3.13 for undergraduates from IAUE, and 3.15 for undergraduates from RSU, implied that the extent of the influence Instagram use on provocative sexual behaviours perceived by undergraduate female students in Rivers State universities based on the identity of the university is to a very high extent.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant influence of Whatsapp use on provocative sexual behaviour as perceived by undergraduate female students in Rivers State universities based on identity.

Table 4: Summary of Independent t-test on the Influence of Whatsapp use on Provocative Sexual Behaviour as Perceived by Undergraduate Female Students in Rivers State Universities Based on Identity

Identity of University	n	\bar{x}	SD	df	t_{cal}	t_{tab}	Sig.	Decision
IAUE	192	12.60	1.46	398	0.50	1.96	0.62	Retain: H_{01}
RSU	208	12.52	1.56					

Table 4 indicates that $t_{cal} = 0.50$, $df = 398$, and $t_{tab} = 1.96$. Therefore, since $t_{cal} < t_{tab}$ and $P = 0.62 > 0.05$, then there is no significant difference in the influence of Whatsapp use on provocative sexual behaviour as perceived by undergraduate female students in Rivers State universities based on identity. Hence, the null hypothesis one is retained at the 0.05 level of significance.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant influence of Facebook on provocative sexual behaviour as perceived by undergraduate female students in Rivers State universities based on the identity of the university.

Table 5: Summary of Independent t-test on the Influence of Facebook on Provocative Sexual Behaviour as Perceived by Undergraduate Female Students in Rivers State Universities Based on the Identity of the University

Identity of University	n	\bar{x}	SD	df	t_{cal}	t_{tab}	Sig.	Decision
IAUE	192	12.45	2.05	398	0.27	1.96	0.79	Retain: H_{09}
RSU	208	12.50	1.86					

Table 5 indicates that $t_{cal} = 0.27$, $df = 398$, and $t_{tab} = 1.96$. Therefore, since $t_{cal} < t_{tab}$ and $P = 0.79 > 0.05$, then there is no significant difference in the influence of Facebook on provocative sexual behaviours perceived by undergraduate female students in Rivers State universities based on the identity of the university. Hence, the null hypothesis two is retained at the 0.05 level of significance.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant influence of Instagram on provocative sexual behaviours perceived by undergraduate female students in Rivers State universities based on the identity of the university.

Table 6: Summary of Independent t-test on the Influence of Instagram on Provocative Sexual Behaviour as Perceived by Undergraduate Female Students in Rivers State Universities Based on the Identity of the University

Identity of University	n	\bar{x}	SD	df	t_{cal}	t_{tab}	Sig.	Decision
IAUE	192	12.49	1.43	398	0.69	1.96	0.49	Retain: H ₀₁₀
RSU	208	12.59	1.37					

Table 6 indicates that $t_{cal} = 0.69$, $df = 398$, and $t_{tab} = 1.96$. Therefore, since $t_{cal} < t_{tab}$ and $P = 0.49 > 0.05$, then there is no significant difference in the influence of Instagram on provocative sexual behaviour as perceived by undergraduate female students in Rivers State universities based on the identity of the university. Hence, the null hypothesis three is retained at the 0.05 level of significance.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The finding of research question one showed that the influence of Whatsapp use on provocative sexual behaviour as perceived by undergraduate female students in Rivers State universities based on the identity of the university is to a very high extent. Furthermore, the result of hypothesis one showed that there is no significant difference in the influence of Whatsapp use on provocative sexual behaviour as perceived by undergraduate female students in Rivers State universities based on identity. The finding is consistent with the finding of Uzobo et al. (2020) which revealed that the use of whatsapp (OR = 0.254, $p < 0.05$), instagram (OR=0.254, $p < 0.05$, time spent on the social media (OR=0.123, $p < 0.05$) were significant associate with high-risk provocative sexual behaviour of students. The study concluded that use of social media especially whatsapp influenced the provocative health needs should be done recognizing the importance of the social media in shopping the health of young people. The study by Adegboyega (2019) also revealed that social media significantly positively correlated with provocative sexual behaviours of the youth. Social media leads student to the act of sending erotic messages, watching pornographic films and movies and risky sexual behaviour such as masturbation. The study also revealed that the use of whatsapp was rated the most used social media in sending and watching provocative pornographic films. The study discovered that friends send their node pictures via whatsapp.

The findings of research question two showed that the influence of Facebook on provocative sexual behaviour as perceived by undergraduate female students in Rivers State universities based on the identity of the university is to a very high extent. Furthermore, the result of hypothesis two showed that there is no significant difference in the influence of Facebook on provocative sexual behaviours perceived by undergraduate female students in Rivers State universities based on the identity of the university.

The finding is consistent with the findings of Uzobo et al. (2020) which revealed that the use of whatsapp (OR = 0.254, $p < 0.05$), instagram (OR=0.254, $p < 0.05$, time spent on the social media (OR=0.123, $p < 0.05$) were significant associate with high-risk provocative sexual behaviour of students. The study concluded that use of social media especially whatsapp influenced the provocative health needs should be done recognizing the importance of the social media in shopping the health of young people. The study by Adegboyega (2019) also revealed that social media significantly positively correlated with provocative sexual behaviours of the youth. Social media leads student to the act of sending erotic messages, watching pornographic films and movies and risky sexual behaviour such as masturbation. The study also revealed that the use of whatsapp was rated the most used social media in sending and watching provocative pornographic films. The study discovered that friends send their node pictures via whatsapp.

The findings of research question ten showed that the influence of Instagram on provocative sexual behaviour as perceived by undergraduate female students in Rivers State universities based on the identity of the university is to a very high extent. Furthermore, the result of hypothesis three showed

that there is no significant difference in the influence of Instagram on provocative sexual behaviours perceived by undergraduate female students in Rivers State universities based on the identity of the university.

The finding is consistent with the findings of Uzobo et al. (2020) which revealed that the use of whatsapp (OR = 0.254, $p < 0.05$), instagram (OR=0.254, $p < 0.05$), time spent on the social media (OR=0.123, $p < 0.05$) were significant associate with high-risk provocative sexual behaviour of students. The study concluded that use of social media especially whatsapp influenced the provocative health needs should be done recognizing the importance of the social media in shopping the health of young people. The study by Adegboyega (2019) also revealed that social media significantly positively correlated with provocative sexual behaviours of the youth. Social media leads student to the act of sending erotic messages, watching pornographic films and movies and risky sexual behaviour such as masturbation. The study also revealed that the use of whatsapp was rated the most used social media in sending and watching provocative pornographic films. The study discovered that friends send their nude pictures via whatsapp. The study by Owen et al. (2020) also revealed that undergraduates in Nigerian universities are largely exposed to a substantial amount of sexual contents on various social media networks; and that this exposure negatively influenced their psychology towards sex as manifested in areas of dating and sexual activities.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were reached: To begin, it is clear that study emphasized the substantial influence of social media platforms such as Whatsapp, Facebook, and Instagram on provocative sexual behaviour. The constant exposure to explicit content, as well as the ease of communication provided by these platforms, may contribute to the normalization and reinforcement of provocative sexual behaviour among female undergraduate students. To mitigate the negative effects on students' sexual behaviour, educational institutions and policymakers must implement comprehensive strategies that not only address psychosocial factors but also promote responsible use of social media.

Counselling Implications

The following were some of the counselling implications:

1. Counselling and developmental centers in our higher institutions should help students and university management to effectively handle the provocative sexual behaviour among students. Counsellors should effectively counsel students against provocative sexual behaviour such as wearing short skirts, wearing sleeveless blouse, seductive sitting and exposure of breast.
2. Counsellors should engage students through seminars, symposiums and conferences to address the effective use of social media by students. Individual and group counselling can also be used to discourage the negative use of social media of Whatsapp, Facebook and Instagram especially against provocative sexual behaviour. Counsellors should expose students to the dangers inherent in negative uses of social media.
3. Counsellors should offer mental health services and resources to support student's emotional well-being because provocative sexual behaviours could be a result of psychological problems.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Universities should establish rules and regulation prohibiting provocative sexual behaviour such as wearing short skirts, wearing sleeveless blouse, seductive sitting and exposure of breast and sharing it via social media.
2. The university management should ensure that students who dress provocatively should not be allowed access into the university premises and the classroom irrespective of the social status of the students.
3. Parents should ensure they have good interactions with their wards on social media to be able to have knowledge of their activities on social media and be able to give support where necessary.

REFERENCES

- Adegboyega, L.O. (2019). Influence of social media on sexual behaviour of youth in Kwara State Nigeria. *Home Archives*, 11(1), 36-49.
- Asyraaf, A. S &Badayai, A. R. A. (2023). Relationship between technology, social media and sexual behaviour among university students. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 12(5), 180-191.
- Darmola, O.E, Adesina, C.T, Adeniran, A &Akande, T.M (2017). Healthcare quality under the matimal health insurance/scheme: A study among patients at a tertiary health institution in Nigeria. *International Journal of Science and Healthcare Research*, 4(1), 303-309.
- Ijadunola, M. Y., Owoeye, I. V., Oyeniyi, D. T &Soile, O. A. (2023). Adolescents in urban and rural communities of Ife Local Government Area, Osun State, Nigeria. *The Global Health Network Conference Proceeding*.Doi:<https://doi.org/1021428/3d48c34a100002901>
- Kolan, B.J&Dzandza, P.E. (2018). Effect of Social media on academic performances of students in Ghanian universities: A case study of university of Ghana, Legon and university of Nebraska-Lincoln. *Journal of Library Philosophy and Practice*, 13(4), 68-81.
- Landry, M. Tuner, M., Vyas, A & Wood, S. (2019). Social media and sexual behaviour among adolescents. *Journal of Medicine and Public Health*, 3(2), 53-71.
- McQuail, D &Deuza, M. (2020). McQuail's media and mass communication theory 7th ed. SAGE Publication
- Obiunu, J. J. (2014). The influence of sexuality education on appropriate sexual behaviours among secondary school students. *Advance Research*, 2(12), 869-878.
- Olawade, D. B., Asaolu, A. J., Adebisi, Y. A., Asaolu, F. t., Odetayo, A & David-Olawede, A. C. (2024). The realities of adolescent sexual behaviours in Nigeria: A narrative review. *African Health Science*, 24(2), 273-282.
- Onasoga, O.A., Alako, J.O., Adegbuyi, S.N., Filade, O.A&Shitto, H.I.B (2020). Influence of social media use of sexual behaviour of under-graduates in Ilorin. Kwara State, Nigeria. *Inter-Disciplinary Journal of Education*, 3(2), 112-122.
- Owem, V. J., Ekpe, M. B. &Eneje, S. (2020). Undergraduates utilization of social networking media and sexual behaviour in higher education: A case study. *Pedagogical Research*, 5(2). em0062.<https://doi.org/10.29333/pr/1940>.
- Pomfowaa, G &Dotse, J. A. (2023). The use of social media as a means of information dissemination among postgraduate students: A case study of the university of Mines and Technology (UMT), TarkwaGhana. *Mining Journal*, 23(1), 34-43. <https://doi.org/10.43/4/gm.v22il.1>
- Popa, T &Delcea, C. (2019). Voyeurism and scopophilia. *International Journal of Advance Studies in Sexology*, 1(1), 53-55.
- Potki, R., Ziaei, T., Faramarzi, M. Moosazadeh, M., &Shahosseini, Z. (2017). Bio-Pscho-social factors affecting sexual self-concept: A systematic review. *Election Physician*, 9(9), 5172-5178.
- Uzob, E., Michael-Olomu, O & Enoch, R.O (2020). Social media use and sexual behaviour of undergraduate students in a Nigerian university. *Journal of Demography and Social Statistics*, 7(2), 1-14.